

Exciplex Formation by Anthracene Monosulphonates in Aqueous Solution and the Role of Nonaqueous Solvents

SUBHASHI CHI BHATTACHARYA, SEKHAR BASU and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE*

Physical Chemistry Laboratory, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 12 February 1993

The absorption and fluorescence spectra of anthracene-1-sulphonate (1-AS), anthracene-2-sulphonate (2-AS), anthracene-1,5-disulphonate (1,5-AS) and anthracene-1,8-disulphonate (1,8-AS), have been studied in a series of polar, protic and aprotic solvents. For monosulphonates the absorption spectra are not much modified in different solvents but emission spectra present a structureless feature in aqueous solution. In nonaqueous solvents vibrational peaks are evident and intensities of fluorescence maxima decrease with blue shift. The disulphonates show normal behaviour. When nonaqueous solvents are gradually added to the aqueous solutions of monosulphonates, vibrational features gradually develop in the fluorescence spectra passing through an isosbestic point. By suitable treatment of data it has been established that the monosulphonates form weak exciplexes with water clusters.

The nature and polarity of a solvent do not have large effect on the absorption and emission spectra of anthracene^{1,2}. On substitution of SO_3^- groups in the ring the compounds become water-soluble but the absorption characteristics of these compounds do not change to any large extent in aqueous solution. On the other hand, considerable changes in their excited state properties³⁻⁵, such as emission characteristics, fluorescence lifetimes, excited state dipole moments and redox potentials⁶, are observed. The sulphonate groups affect the overall symmetry property of the anthracene moiety and also introduce negatively charged centres in the molecules. The electron distribution of electronically excited molecules can be described experimentally by the measurement of the excited state dipole moments, a quantity which is often obtained from the measurement of solvatochromic shifts of absorption and fluorescence spectra^{5,7-12}.

The effect of solvent on absorption and emission spectra of anthracene sulphonates has been studied earlier^{5,12-14}. The emission spectra of monosulphonates are sensitive to solvent¹²⁻¹⁴. Specially, 1-AS gives a completely structureless emission spectrum in aqueous solution which develops vibrational features on addition of ACN, EtOH, EG, THF

etc., even on incorporation in the Triton X-100 micelles¹⁴. It appears that the interaction is very specific for H_2O . Evidences are that an exciplex with one or two water molecules is formed in the excited state. A detailed analysis of the data and a more quantitative information is sought in this paper.

The experimental conditions are the same as reported earlier^{4-6,12-14}.

Results and Discussion

It is normally assumed that sulphonate group is a very weak perturbant of the parent molecule in the ground energy state of the molecule. But in the electronically excited state the situation is not as simple as revealed by our earlier studies⁶ on mono- and disubstituted anthracene sulphonates, 1-AS, 2-AS, 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS. The absorption spectra of these four compounds in aqueous medium are very similar to each other except for small red-shift on substitution of SO_3^- group with reference to anthracene in benzene^{12,13}. No red-shift is observed for longitudinally substituted 2-AS as compared to anthracene in benzene since transition moment of longest wave (1L_a) absorption band of anthracene is γ -polarised. The molar extinction for 1,8-AS is reduced to 1/4 of that for others and is apparently

caused by distortion of the molecule due to two bulky sulphonate groups (SO_3^-) on the same side of the molecule, on two counts : (i) due to steric effect and (ii) due to electrostatic repulsion. But considerable variation is observed in the nature of the emission spectra. Anomalously large Stokes' shift (Table 1) and lack of vibrational features for 1-AS and to some extent for 2-AS suggest specific solute-solvent interaction in the excited state. Although emission spectrum of 1,5-AS has vibrational features exactly similar to anthracene in benzene, a red-shift of about 480 cm^{-1} is observed in aqueous solution. The vibrational features are present for 1,8-AS also. The specific solute-solvent interaction was not so serious for other solvents like ethanol (EtOH), methanol (MeOH), formamide (FMD), tetrahydrofuran (THF), acetonitrile (ACN), ethylene glycol (EG) and few others¹²⁻¹⁴. In these solvents fluorescence spectra (Figs. 1 and 2) exhibit definite vibrational features (more or less extent), more in EtOH, ACN, THF and less in FMD, EG etc. The vibrational features appear also when incorporated in micelles¹⁴ of Triton X-100.

TABLE 1 – ABSORPTION AND EMISSION CHARACTERISTICS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION AND STOKES' SHIFT OF FLUORESCENCE FOR ANTHRACENE SULPHONATES

Compd.	$\lambda_{\text{abs}}^{\text{max}}$	$\bar{\nu}_{\text{abs}}^{\text{max}}$	$\lambda_{\text{f}}^{\text{max}}$	$\bar{\nu}_{\text{f}}^{\text{max}}$	$(\bar{\nu}_{\text{abs}}^{\text{max}} - \bar{\nu}_{\text{f}}^{\text{max}})$
1-AS	363	27 550	420	23 809	3 740
2-AS	360	27 977	414	24 213	3 764
1,5-AS	364	27 472	411	24 330	3 142
1,8-AS	368	27 173	417	23 970	3 203
1-AS (ACN)	361	27 800	407	24 600	3 200
Anthracene (C_6H_6)	358	27 932	402	24 850	3 082

On gradual addition of ACN to an aqueous solution of 1-AS, the vibrational features gradually develop, the λ_{max} is shifted to the blue and the intensity of fluorescence emission decreases. The same behaviour is observed for 2-AS but for 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS, the emission intensity increase continuously on going from aqueous solution to ACN solution. These differences are brought out effectively when fluorescence intensities are plotted as a function of mole fraction of ACN in the solution (Fig. 3). A sharp initial drop in intensity is observed which then levels off for higher fraction of ACN. The same type of variations is observed for other

Fig. 1. Fluorescence spectra of $8 \times 10^{-5} M$ anthracene 1-sulphonate in water-acetonitrile mixture : I to VII in 0, 10, 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100% water respectively (λ in nm).

mixed solvents like EtOH, THF etc. and they all fall on the same curve, except for FMD and EG, for which there is a gradual decrease in intensity. For 1,5- and 1,8-AS there is no initial decrease, the intensity of emission at $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{f}}$ increases continuously

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of $8 \times 10^{-5} M$ anthracene 1-sulphonate in water-formamide mixture : I to IV in 20, 40, 60 and 80 % water respectively.

Fig. 3 Plots of maximum fluorescence intensity in quanta per unit wavenumber interval at $23\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for 1-AS and $23\,980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for 2-AS against the mole fraction of the solvent in solvent-water mixture: (O) ethyl alcohol, (⊗) ethylene glycol, (●) acetonitrile, (Δ) tetrahydrofuran and (○) formamide. For 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS there is continuous increase.

as a function of added second solvent although there is some amount of discrepancy for 1,8-AS. The opposite nature of solvent effects for the same set of solvents for mono- and disulphonates cannot be fully explained by the dielectric constants of the components of the binary solvent mixture. These observations had been explained earlier^{5,13} by involving intramolecular bonding interaction of the charge transfer type between the SO_3^- group and the excited electronic system of the anthracene ring and the role of symmetry of the CT dipoles thus

created. Considering the differences in the behaviour of mono- and disulphonates, the symmetry and dipole moments of the molecules in the excited state seem to be very relevant.

A plausible approach which can explain the opposite trends in fluorescence behaviour of mono- and disulphonates is to assume definite solute-solvent interactions in the excited state. The observed anomalous effect of the mixed solvents on 1-AS and 2-AS can then be treated on the basis of solvent adsorption model where primary solvent occupies fixed sites on the surface of the solute molecule. Assuming that the Langmuir's adsorption isotherm should be applicable, if γ is the fraction of sites occupied, then we can work out the following expression following Lippert¹⁵,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= \frac{n}{n_{\max}} = \frac{\text{Number of sites occupied}}{\text{Maximum number of sites available}} \\ &= \text{Fraction of sites occupied} \\ &= \frac{F_0 - F}{F_0 - F_{\max}} \end{aligned}$$

where, F_0 is the fluorescence intensity in absence of second solvent, F the fluorescence intensity in presence of second solvent and F_{\max} the constant intensity of fluorescence reached finally on further addition of the second solvent.

If we consider the specific case of $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{ACN}$ system, on gradual addition of ACN to 1-AS, ACN molecules displace water molecules initially adsorbed on a definite number of sites available on the solute molecules. One can correlate the fractional change in the fluorescence intensity to fractional displacement of H_2O molecules by ACN. Using a mass action type equilibrium,

where, M_L is the added solvent molecules free in solution phase, S the number of sites available on the solute surface and M_A the number of solvent molecules adsorbed on the surface of solute molecules, i.e. number of sites occupied by the added solvent molecules.

If C_A and C_L are the concentrations of the second solvent in the adsorbed and the free state such that the total concentration C is

$$C = C_A + C_L$$

$$\approx C_L \text{ (since } C_L \gg C_A) \approx X$$

the equilibrium constant K ,

$$K = \frac{[M_A]}{[M_L][S]} = \frac{C_A}{C_L C_S} \approx \frac{C_A}{C C_S}$$

where, C_S is the concentration of sites available for adsorption.

$$\text{Therefore } KC \approx \frac{C_A}{C_S} = \frac{n}{n_{\max} - n} = \frac{n/n_{\max}}{1 - \frac{n}{n_{\max}}}$$

$$\frac{1}{KC} = \frac{1-y}{y} = \frac{1}{y} - 1$$

$$\text{and } \frac{1}{y} = 1 + \frac{1}{KC} \quad (1)$$

where, $y = n/n_{\max}$. The expression resembles the one for Langmuir's adsorption isotherm. When $1/y$, derived from the experimental data is plotted as a function of $1/C$, where C is the concentration of the second solvent ACN in solution, linear plots are obtained for both 1-AS and 2-AS (Fig. 4). From the slope of the plots one can calculate the value of K , the equilibrium constant for the solute-solvent interactions. A value of $K=5 M^{-1}$ for 1-AS and $3 M^{-1}$ for 2-AS have been computed. The difference is understandable in terms of the electron-withdrawing property of SO_3^- in 1-position, the excited state dipole moments of 1-AS and 2-AS and the y -polarised nature of the 1L_a transition in the anthracene moiety.

From these considerations it can be definitely said that water molecules are clustered around the solute molecule, most probably at the SO_3^- site in the case of 1-AS and 2-AS by specific interaction forming a solvated complex in the excited state. Addition of ACN destroys the complex. It can be said that monosulphonates form an exciplex with definite number of water molecules. The dif-

Fig. 4 Plot of $1/y$ vs $1/c$: (O) 1-AS and (●) 2-AS

ference 540 cm^{-1} in Stoke's shift (Table 1) between completely solvated species of 1-AS and of that in ACN may be assigned as the energy of interaction with H_2O molecules. No such interaction is observed for 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS due to more symmetrical nature of disulphonates. The enhancement of fluorescence for 1,5-AS and 1,8-AS on addition of aprotic and other solvents is due to general solvent effect as compared to specific solute-solvent interaction observed for monosulphonates.

Excited state dipole moments and redox potentials:

Since the solvation properties are greatly affected by the polar nature of the solute, the dipole moments of these compounds have been calculated⁵ using a series of solvents of different polarity parameter and using the technique of Sun and Song¹⁶. The values are reported in Table 2. Large changes in dipole moment on excitation ($\Delta\mu$) for 1-AS and zero dipole moment for 1,5-AS explain the phenomenon to some extent. Assuming no H-bonded exciplex formation for 1,5-AS, similar to that for 1-AS, the difference in Stoke's shift works out to be 600 cm^{-1} , very near to the difference between

H₂O and ACN as solvents for 1-AS.TABLE 2—DIPOLE MOMENTS IN THE GROUND (μ_g) AND EXCITED STATE (μ_e) OF ANTHRACENE SULPHONATES AND THEIR REDUCTION POTENTIAL VALUES

Compd	μ_g Debye	μ_e Debye	μ Debye	$E_{1/2}$ (eV) vs NHE	$E_{1/2}^*$
1-AS	0.8 ± 0.2	4.4 ± 0.2	3.6	-1.58	+1.60
2-AS	5.8 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.1	0.9	-1.66 ^a	+1.52
1,5-AS	0.0	0.0	0.0	-1.51	+1.70
1,8-AS	3.8 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.1	2.9	-1.71 ^a	+1.50

^aEstimated value

The polarographic reduction potentials of these compounds⁶ also vary considerably among themselves. The values are given in Table 2. These values establish that SO₃⁻ groups are electron-withdrawing in the ground state leaving the anthracene skeleton charge deficient. The 1,5-AS with two symmetrically placed SO₃⁻ groups has lowest reduction potential and zero dipole moment. Small dipole moment is observed for 1-AS and fairly large value for 2-AS in absence of such compensation. Actually 2-AS and 1,8-AS could not be reduced polarographically in aqueous solution. For 1,8-AS large dipole moment even in ground state is primarily due to the presence of SO₃⁻ groups in 1,8-positions and the value is increased on excitation due to γ -polarised excitation. The electron affinity and ionisation potentials both increase on excitation. The excited state redox potential $E_{1/2}^*$ indicates that these compounds become good electron-acceptors on excitation⁶.

Excited state lifetimes : The specific solvation in excited state, a kind of exciplex formation with a number of H₂O molecules for 1-AS is further confirmed from the measured lifetime data τ_1 (H₂O) in aqueous solution. Table 3 presents the observed and calculated lifetimes for these four compounds in water and ACN. The theoretical values are based on Stickler-Berg expression¹⁷ and observed data are obtained by single photon counting technique^{3,4,19}. Calculated lifetimes based on the expression, $\tau^{cal} = \tau^{theo} \times \Phi_f$, are recorded in Table 3. Φ_f is the quantum yield of fluorescence. It is found that (i) observed lifetime for 1-AS is much larger than the value expected from the quantum yield data, $\Phi_f \times \tau_0^{theo}$ (7.30 ns compared to 3.42 ns), (ii)

τ (ACN) for 1-AS is closer to the expected value, and (iii) quantum yields do not follow the order of lifetime data, τ_f is highest for 2-AS.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF LIFETIME τ FOR VARIOUS ANTHRACENE SULPHONATES IN H₂O DETERMINED BY VARIOUS METHODS

Compd	τ^{theo} ns	τ^{calc} ns	τ^{photon} (ns)*	
			H ₂ O	ACN
1-AS	13.7	3.4	7.30	2.6
2-AS	11.8	4.7	4.50	4.9
1,5-AS	14.5	3.8	3.22	3.8
1,8-AS	40.8	6.5	1.46	1.9

* $\tau^{photon} = \tau$ obtained by single photon counting technique

The large value of τ_1 (H₂O) for 1-AS, points to its solvated structure. The τ_1 (ACN) is much smaller and nearer to expected value. The lifetime of 1-AS measured at three different wavelengths of emission (Table 4) show slight variations, although the variations may be said to be within the experimental error. Such variations also confirm the formation of exciplexes which is further substantiated by the τ_1 values in water + ACN mixed solvents. As the proportion of water is decreased, τ_1 tends to that in pure ACN.

TABLE 4—LIFETIME τ OF 1-AS IN MIXED SOLVENT OF H₂O AND ACN AT DIFFERENT WAVELENGTHS

	τ_1 (400 nm)	τ_2 (420 nm)	τ_3 (450 nm)
	ns	ns	ns
H ₂ O	7.3	7.4	7.6
H ₂ O ACN (1 : 1)		2.8	3.4
H ₂ O ACN (1 : 2)		2.6	
ACN		2.6	

Temperature effects : The quantum yields for fluorescence emission Φ_f were found to be a function of temperature even for a small variation near room temperature. Assuming thermal quenching to occur through intersystem crossing to triplet state, from the temperature dependence of fluorescence quantum yields the energy of activation ΔE_a has been identified^{3,4,19} with energy barrier to ISC (intersystem crossing). Such barrier has been observed previously¹⁸ and has been equated with S_1-T_x energy difference, where T_x is a higher triplet with reference to the lowest T_1 state. The higher value of ΔE_a for 2-AS explains higher Φ_f for this compound caused

by decreased probability of ISC. Apparently substitution of SO_3^- group at different sites lowers the respective S_1 state to different extent since higher triplet is supposed not to be much perturbed by solvent and substituents. The temperature dependence of T-T absorption¹⁹ also predicts small barrier heights for ISC.

Another source for temperature dependence may arise due to breaking of water structure around the monosulphonates. Further information on this point was sought from quenching experiments using small inorganic anions as quenchers. The temperature dependence for quenching was studied⁶ for 1-AS, 2-AS and 1,5-AS using I^- and Br^- as quenchers. The k_q was found to be temperature dependent for 1-AS and 2-AS only but not for 1,5-AS. Therefore the temperature dependence of quenching cannot be accounted for by temperature dependence of solvent viscosity alone but rather the role of solvation-desolvation phenomenon is emphasised. A considerable solvent reorganisation is required in order that highly solvated quencher ions approach within the effective sphere of action for quenching of fluorescence of a solvated fluorescer. The activation enthalpy and entropy and the free energy of activation, calculated from the data for temperature dependence are given in Table 5. The temperature dependence of 1-AS and 2-AS and none for 1,5-AS again suggests solvated nature of the monosulphonates in the first excited state.

TABLE 5—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR QUENCHING OF ANTHRACENE SULPHONATES BY INORGANIC ANIONS⁶

Compd	Quencher	ΔH^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger eu	ΔG^\ddagger kcal mol ⁻¹
1-AS	I^-	3.54	-1.70	4.05
	Br^-	3.84	-10.10	6.85
2-AS	I^-	3.84	+1.28	3.46
	Br^-	1.36	-13.68	5.44
1,5-AS	I^-	0	0	0
	Br^-	0	0	0

In another set of experiments the temperature dependence of fluorescence of 1-AS was measured as a function of solvent mixture $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{ACN}$. The energy of activation (ΔE_a kJ mol⁻¹) data calculated from Arrhenius type plots are as follows :

H_2O , 10.28; $\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{ACN}$ (1 : 1), 5.14; $\text{H}_2\text{O} : \text{ACN}$ (1 : 2), 4.68; ACN , 0.0. In aqueous solution of 1-AS, the energy of activation is 10.28 kJ mol⁻¹ which decreases on gradual addition of ACN, and becomes zero for the solution in pure ACN. The results demonstrate that no temperature dependence is observed for solution of 1-AS in ACN. Now if ACN is considered as reference solvent where there is no specific solvation, the difference in λ_f^{max} between the solutions in ACN and H_2O is expected to give the binding energy for water molecules. From the fluorescence data : for 1-AS, $\bar{\nu}_f^{\text{max}}$ in ACN = 24 600 cm⁻¹ and in H_2O = 23 809 cm⁻¹, the difference between the two, 791 cm⁻¹ = 9.45 kJ mol⁻¹, is very close to the observed value of ΔE_a in aqueous solution and can be identified with the energy of formation of the complex.

Excited state interactions with other solvents :

Of the solvents studied (Fig. 3) two of them, formamide (FMD) and ethylene glycol (EG), show linear decrease in quantum efficiency with mole fraction of solvent in solvent-water mixture, the slope being greater for EG than for FMD. Also for $\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{FMD}$ system, slope is greater for 2-AS than that for 1-AS. On the other hand, other solvents EtOH, ACN, THF show nonlinear variation with solvent composition as already discussed for ACN, a sharp decrease upto $X = 0.4$ followed by levelling off before reaching the pure solvent. The points for all the three solvents fall on the same curve and accordingly can be treated in the similar manner to ACN + H_2O mixture. The levelling off occurs at $X \approx 0.3$ for 1-AS and $X \approx 0.4$ for 2-AS. Although the excited state dipole moment μ_e of 2-AS is 6.7 Debye, the difference from the ground state value $\mu_g = 5.8$ D is 0.9 only as compared to 1-AS which is 4.4 Debye. The dielectric constants of the two solvents FMD and EG are 109.5 and 40.7 although the value of $E_{1(30)}$ is the same 56.6 and 56.8 respectively. The dielectric constant of H_2O is 78.5. These observations suggest that no specific solvent-solvent interactions are involved between these two solvents, the continuum models of solvent structure is valid and the solute-solvent interactions are guided by the excited state dipole moments mainly.

On the other hand, for the solvents like EtOH, ACN and THF, D_{250} (D_{250} = dielectric constant at 25°) being 24.55, 35.9 and 7.58 respectively, compared to water 78.5, the solvatochromic shifts in F_1^{\max} and quantum yields of fluorescence are non-linear. According to Suppan²⁰ this non-linearity results from the general process of 'dielectric enrichment' of the solvent shell of dipolar molecules due to preferential solvation of the solute dipole. In mixed solvents such as H₂O + EtOH or H₂O + ACN, the continuum model at a distance, will become structured near the polar solute molecules. Water preferentially solvates the sulphonic acid group of 1-AS and 2-AS in the excited state. Further, the points for EtOH + H₂O and THF + H₂O, all fall on the same curve as that for ACN + H₂O (Fig. 4). All these suggest that the interaction with water is of specific solute-solvent type, water molecules forming complexes in the excited state with monosulphonates. These complexes are designated as exciplexes.

References

1. S. R. VELJKOVIC, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 1181.
2. N. MATAGA, Y. KAIFU and M. KOIZUMI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1956, **29**, 465.
3. A. K. GUPTA, S. BASU and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1980, **58**, 1046.
4. S. BASU and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *J. Lumin.*, 1984, **28**, 39.
5. SEKHAR BASU and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 1147.
6. K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE and S. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1988, **44**, 289, and references therein.
7. P. SUPPAN, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1983, **94**, 272.
8. K. M. C. DAVIS in "Molecular Association", ed. R. FOSTER, Academic, New York, 1975, p. 151.
9. E. LIPPERT, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1957, **61**, 962.
10. N. G. BAKHSHIEV, *Opt. Spectrosc.*, 1962, **12**, 309.
11. P. SUPPAN, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1968, **24**, 1161.
12. K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE and B. P. SINGH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 595.
13. A. K. GUPTA, B. P. SINGH and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 382.
14. S. K. BHATTACHARYA and K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 50.
15. E. LIPPERT in "Organic Molecular Photophysics", Vol. 2, ed. J. B. BIRKS, Wiley, New York, 1975.
16. M. SUN and P. S. SONG, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1977, **25**, 3.
17. S. J. STRICKLER and R. A. BERG, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **37**, 814.
18. M. S. WALKER, T. W. BEDNAR, R. LUMRY and F. HUMPHRY, *Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1971, **14**, 147.
19. K. K. ROHATGI-MUKHERJEE, K. BHATTACHARYA and P. K. DAS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2*, 1985, **81**, 1331.
20. P. SUPPAN, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1* 1987, **83**, 495.

